

Preliminary analysis to identify key areas of carbon depleted/saturated soils in Scotland, broken down by farm type

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Executive summary

Current knowledge	Limitations and future data needs
<p>[1] Current understanding, supported by soil survey data, indicates grassland soils maintain larger soil carbon concentrations and stocks, relative to arable soils.</p> <p>[2] The capacity of soils to store carbon is strongly influenced by soil type (e.g., heavy texture > light).</p> <p>[3] Existing soils data allows the range of carbon concentrations achievable across soil types to be estimated.</p> <p>[4] Current understanding is that changing agricultural management (e.g., arable to grass) can significantly increase soil carbon, albeit over long timescales.</p> <p>[5] Scotland's cultivated soils currently have relatively high carbon contents, but directed management could increase these stocks and serve to protect existing stocks.</p> <p>[6] Options such as regenerative practices and mixed farming, including livestock, have potential to foster enhanced carbon storage. However, the scientific evidence for this still developing (e.g., context-specificity), and will require broader assessments (e.g., life-cycle analyses) to quantify GHG benefits.</p>	<p>[1] Current field assessments of soil carbon are not at the resolution to allow determinations of a baseline of field-scale carbon status in combination with SIACS management data.</p> <p>[2] Soil type and land use are not independent of each other. The economic options for land management and the implementation of nature-based solutions are constrained by soil type and the wider land capability for the provision of ecosystem services. This limits the assessment of soil type x management impacts on soil carbon based on currently available data.</p> <p>[3] Combining data sets, based on statistical methods developed within the SRP, could provide additional data to establish a baseline against which to measure changes in soil carbon and link them to management practices.</p> <p>[4] Data collected as part of the whole farm plan would provide evidence to support Agri-environment schemes. The use of this data would require the spatial locations of the sampling points and consistent metadata on sampling and laboratory methods.</p> <p>[5] Understanding the carbon stored in soils and their capacity to store more (and to assess risks of losses) requires an integrated understanding of biological and physical processes, that is captured within modelling frameworks to predict trajectories of change (e.g., management and climate scenarios).</p>

1. Introduction

Scope of the report

This document sets out an overview of the data sets that are available to help understand which farm types may have depleted soil organic carbon (SOC) and where there may be value in focussing efforts to improve farm carbon balances. It also outlines the purposes for which different data sets were developed and therefore their value for use within the wider stakeholder debate.

When using data to understand whether soils have “depleted carbon” the question being asked is “What is the status of the SOC with respect to a reference?”. In this case the reference is “farm type” or more technically a combination of soil type, land management, and other environmental factors. When focussing efforts to “improve SOC balances” there is then a need to understand the potential for soils to increase or lose SOC and the stability of the SOC within the soil.

We know that Scotland’s soils are comparatively C-rich and that specific soil types differ in their capacity to store carbon. This understanding allows the carbon stock of soils to be benchmarked within ranges of comparable soils. This can then be used to highlight where there are significant risks of carbon losses through poor management (and climate change feedbacks); as well as potential benefits to be realised from increased C-storage.

The aim of this document is to discuss the data that are available to understand the current status of carbon stocks in cultivated soils (both arable and improved grassland) and provide an overview of how future data and research can be used to improve robust decision making and advice.

To achieve these objectives we will provide an overview of:

- Data on the current status and changes in soil carbon and its stability.
- Work done to link SOC to reference values, or set them within a distribution.
- Measured data and modelling approaches that can help understand the potential of soils to increase their carbon stocks

This document is a high-level overview of data sets and current research that may be available to help identify SOC depletion on farms and where efforts may be targeted, but available data does not allow assessments at an individual farm level.

Soil Carbon and Carbon turnover in soils

Natural biogeochemical cycles mediate exchange of C between soils and the atmosphere (Figure 1). The equilibrium soil C status is a function of both the magnitude of plant inputs and soil processes mediating consumption of soil organic matter (SOM). This balance is dependent

on environment factors, land use and intrinsic soil properties. For agricultural soils, the balance is also strongly affected by management practice.

Figure 1: Soil Organic Carbon processing, drivers and impacts

In Scotland, soils have both mineral and peaty topsoils. The large majority of Scotland's intensively managed soils have mineral topsoils and this report presents the data and evidence for these soils.

2. Soil Organic Carbon Status

Mapping SOC concentration and stocks

There have been several initiatives to map SOC across Scotland. Outputs of these are maps providing national-scale assessments of carbon stocks and regional trends. They are not designed to be able to identify individual fields with depleted SOC and several factors need to be considered when using the results to feed into the wider debate on SOC. This includes the age of the measured SOC data and the range of land management/soil type it represents, as well as the purpose of the original mapping or modelling exercise.

Previous mapping approaches have been outlined in Lilly & Baggaley 2021. The main aim of the most recent carbon stock mapping was to assess the presence of peat at a more detailed resolution (10 m grid) than had been previously attempted (Robb et al., 2025). Although focused on peat, this data also generated maps of SOC stocks across all soils (Figure 2). An attempt was made to intersect these stocks with land management classes based on the from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) to obtain an assessment of current status of carbon in different land use intensity classes.

Figure 2: Maps of Carbon stocks mapped on a normalised scale from 0 to 1 (Robb et al., 2025) and data representing land management intensity based on IACS data

The mean SOC concentrations and stocks do not show consistent trends between different definitions of land management intensity (Figure 3) and there is large uncertainty within each of these classes. These results are not unexpected as even though an output from the model is a map of SOC stock at a 10 m grid, the modelling does not explicitly include field-based land management intensity. The key aim of the modelling was to map peat and peaty soils and therefore the majority of the input data was peat depth measurements and SOC stocks within uncultivated peat and peaty soils rather than the predominantly mineral soils associated with arable and improved grassland (Robb et al., 2025). In addition care needs to be taken when analysing the modelled SOC data within the IACS land management classes as there are mismatches, even between the arable and improved grassland classes (2 of 9 classes based on the UK CEH land cover map) used in the modelling, and what is mapped as arable and improved grassland in using the IACS data.

Figure 3: Average soil organic carbon stocks by (a) The count of arable years in a 7-year rotation and (b) The count of arable land in a 7-year rotation corrected for high intensity crops such as route crops

3. Measured data from across Scotland

Carbon stocks and concentrations from national data sets

A key data set that provides evidence on the spatial variability of soil carbon concentrations and stocks is the National Soil Inventory of Scotland (NSIS1 providing 10 km grid across Scotland, with increased points from a 5 km grid for arable and improved grassland) and the wider sets of data from Scotland's soils database

Within Scotland's soils data there is more extensive assessments of carbon concentrations than stocks. To obtain an estimate of soil carbon stocks, soil carbon concentration, bulk density and the thickness of the soil layers being considered are needed.

An analysis of SOC (Figure 4) with observed land management at the time of sampling shows increasing SOC stocks and concentrations from arable < intensive grassland < extensive grassland. This is consistent with scientific understanding of the generally positive impacts of reduced soil disturbance, continuous plant cover and increased plant diversity on soil carbon storage.

Figure 4: (a) Mean SOC stocks and standard deviations (t C ha) and sample size of arable land, and improved grassland to 100 cm depth derived from the National Soil Inventory of Scotland 2007-9 (b) Mean and standard deviations and sample size of topsoils under arable, rotational grassland and permanent grassland at the time of sampling from the Scottish Soils Database.

There are many regional and national data sets outlined in Lilly & Baggaley 2021 and although few were collected to specifically investigate change in SOC over time, some could be adapted to do this. If a combination of these data sets were resampled there would be the opportunity to link them to time series of IACS land use data to investigate in more detail the impact of land use and management on SOC stocks. Robust statistical advice would also be needed to establish how currently available and new datasets could be amalgamated and how modelling and experimental results could be incorporated to better identify where SOC stocks could be increased.

Combining data sets for analysis

Due to spatial heterogeneity in soil carbon distributions (even within single fields) there is ongoing research within the SRP, using NSIS and other datasets, to determine the number of sampling points needed to detect a specified magnitude of change in carbon stocks for different land uses at a national scale (Appendix 1, Potts et al., 2024).

This work is continuing within the SRP and will assess the data sets that can be robustly combined to generate a baseline (initially for SOC) and also develop statistical methods for combining currently available and future data sets. The work will also provide an assessment of the points where detailed, full soil profile descriptions are available and their statistical representation for providing an underpinning data set for a soil monitoring framework.

It is understood from conversations with Scottish Government that data from the National test program is in the possession of farmers without records being collated by Scottish Government and therefore is not a suitable data set to pursue.

However, data collected going forward as part of the Whole Farm Plan could provide a baseline data set for assessments of the impacts of Agri-Environment Schemes. The use of this data would require:

- Spatial locations of the fields (if an aggregated sample is collected from a field) or sampling points (if a set of individual points) so the data can be linked to farm management and mapped soils, landscape and climate data.
- The recording of consistent metadata is essential to account for possible differences in:
 - How samples were taken in a field or over an area in non-cultivated sites. For example: whether one point is sampled to represent an area or whether samples from a series of points across an area are taken and aggregated.
 - The analytical methods for example the temperature at which loss on ignition (a measure of carbon in the soil) is analysed, where higher temperatures will lead to greater values that would need to be taken into account if they were to be used with data from analysis at lower temperatures.

The 'Big Data' generated from farm-scale monitoring may help give an overall picture of change but there are potential biases due to differences in methods used to collect the data and the fact that the locations sampled may not be representative. By integrating data from farm-scale monitoring with data from a designed survey it may be possible to obtain better estimates than either would provide individually, but this will only be possible if there is the ability to store and analyse the data centrally. Other considerations in using these data would be issues of data ownership and the trust of farmers in the purpose for which the data would be used.

Other farm data sets being reviewed as part of RESAS Underpinning National Capacity by SRUC include historical and more recent SAC on-farm data collected as part of the farm advisory service.

Ranges of Soil Organic Carbon

Scotland's soils are comparatively C-rich and there is significant risk resulting from bad management (and climate change feedbacks); as well as potential benefits to be realised from increased C-storage. Based on Scotland's soil database it is possible to define where measured soil carbon lies within a range of comparable soils under specific land uses. Initial assessments have been made of the ranges of SOC that can occur within cultivated versions of individual soil types (Lilly & Baggaley, 2021) and are a useful starting point to interpret SOC data that could be collected in field-scale monitoring. Summary data for cultivated soils (combined grassland and arable) can be found on Scotland's soil website. This provides ranges of soil carbon

concentrations for the soil series within National Soil map from Scotland's Soils Knowledge and Information Base (SSKIB) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Data available on Scotland's soils website on the ranges of soil carbon based on similar soil types under cultivation. Data shown are for the surface (Ap- Ploughed) horizon of different soil types https://map.environment.gov.scot/Soil_maps/?layer=1#

Scotland's soils data can also be used in combination with climate and other environmental factors in models that will provide predictions of the potential for changes in SOC associated with land management changes. The application of these models as part of Farm Carbon Calculators requires measured farm SOC and a knowledge of the current management.

Long term experimental plots

The literature shows that the magnitude of change in SOC as a result of changes in management is not the same for all soil types or from all baseline positions or previous management history. Having detailed data across soil types is important for understanding the processes that are driving changes in soil carbon, and the impact of changes on other soil properties and functions.

There are a number of experimental farms across Scotland that include JHI farms at Balruddery, Grieves House and Glensnaugh and those linked to SRUC and the other Main Research Providers. These farms cover both intensively managed arable and grassland and upland extensive agriculture. At the long-term experimental plots at Grieves House and the Balruddery Centre for Sustainable Cropping, trajectories of soil organic carbon concentrations have been measured for different management practices.

These experiments show that:

- Long term management using no-tillage has increased carbon concentrations in the topsoil compared to ploughed plots at Grieves House (Figure6).
- Sustainable management (a combination of reduced agrochemicals and soil disturbance, crop diversification, increasing biodiversity and integrated pest

management) at Balruddery has increased carbon concentrations in the topsoil compared to conventional practice (Figure 7).

Figure 6: SOC concentrations in long term experiments comparing no Till and ploughed plots at Grieves House experimental farm

Figure 7: SOC concentrations in long term experiments comparing Conventional and Integrated tillage at the Centre for Sustainable Cropping at Balruddery experimental farm

These experiments allow both the assessment of SOC change but also the detailed assessment of other indicators that help to explain how and why these changes may be occurring and therefore where similar or different results may be reproduced. This includes work on exploring links between time series of soil properties (biological, physical and chemical) to provide a proxy for soil processes that can be linked to SOC stocks and turnover

Although, relationships between management practices and SOC have been shown on these experimental plots, more data would be required to allow generalisations to be made across all environmental and soil type gradients in Scotland.

Carbon associated with the fine fraction of soils

Carbon contained within soil is often considered to consist of distinct fractions that differ in their stability (i.e., with differential rates of decomposition). SOC in agricultural soils can be protected from decomposition due to chemical recalcitrance, physical protection and association with soil minerals (Figure 8). Mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) is particularly important in the context of soil C-sequestration, as this fraction has been considered to represent a long-term storage pool, more resistant to rapid losses due to climate and management. The importance of MAOM is reflected in known positive relationships between silt and clay contents and soils' capacity to store carbon (Hassink, 1997).

Figure 8: Mineral associated and particulate organic matter. Source: <https://www.green-technology.org/soil-carbon-is-a-valuable-resource/>

As existing soil data includes measures of particle size distributions, there is potential to estimate soil-specific C-storage potential from abundance of silt and clay fractions (Figure 9). To fully realise this potential, relationships would need to be fine-tuned for the wetter and cooler climatic conditions of Scotland, relative to conditions for which the Hassink equations were originally developed. In addition to climate affecting these relationships, ongoing research within the SRP is demonstrating significant influences of the mineralogy of clay fractions in stabilisation of carbon. As this mineralogical data from X-Ray Diffraction is also available (NSIS) and represents a 'static' feature of specific soil types, there is strong potential for use in refined predictions of a soil's carbon storage potential. With development, this approach could be directly supported by Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FT-IR) spectroscopy which provides integrated, qualitative measures of soil organic and mineral fractions, and is now available for portable, hand-held devices suitable for field surveys.

Figure 9: NSIS1 (1978-88) mineral topsoil total SOC concentrations showing the SOC predicted to be associated with minerals (a) Improved grassland (b) Arable

Characterisation of different soil fractions is important both for predictions of stability of current carbon stocks and to allow parameterisation of models for prediction of future trajectories of change. As described FT-IR provides an approach to characterise the composition of soil fractions, and others such as Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) where the differential thermodynamic stability of soil carbon fractions is used to quantify their relative abundance in soil. In a practical monitoring context, these and similar approaches could be used to quantify stabilised carbon, and differentiate this from transient forms (e.g., manure) and from inorganic carbon (e.g., from liming).

4. Conclusions and recommendations

- The intersection of the latest available SOC stock mapping (Robb et al., 2025) with IACS management data demonstrated that this use of the data is not a robust way for identifying farms with depleted SOC stocks.
- Data from the Scottish Soil Profile Database shows that the status of SOC concentration increases from arable < intensive grassland < extensive grassland.
- Work within the SRP has assessed the number of sampling points needed to detect a specified magnitude of change in carbon stocks for different land uses at a national scale. This work is being continued to assess how data sets can be combined to provide robust national level assessments of SOC.
- Measured SOC stocks and concentrations from within Scotland's soil database can be used to provide ranges for similar soil types, within which the context new measurements can be assessed.
- Process based modelling of SOC allows the exploration of rates and magnitudes of changes as a result of different land managements.
- Data from long term experimental farm platform sites allow management impacts on SOC to be linked to shifts in biological, chemical and physical soil parameters, providing indicators of SOC accrual trajectories and supporting site-specific targeting of beneficial management strategies.
- Characterisation of the different fractions of SOC, and particularly their associations with mineral particles, is an important component of assessing which farm locations could be more likely to lose or increase SOC concentrations and stocks.
- Data collected as part of the Whole Farm Plan could provide a useful big data set to help address questions on the drivers of soil carbon change.

References

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